

Facile synthesis of iron oxide NPs as magnetically recyclable catalysts for chemoselective synthesis of pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridine-5-carbonitriles in aqueous medium under ultrasonic irradiation[†]

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Abstract : A magnetically recoverable iron oxide nanocatalyst has been prepared at room temperature by a wet chemical technique. This catalyst was characterized by XRD, TEM and EDAX. The results show that the particles are mostly spherical in shape and have an average size of approximately 17 nm. These nanoparticles were exploited to study their catalytic activities towards the chemoselective synthesis of pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridine derivatives. The method showed remarkable selectivity for pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridines over dehydrogenated pyrazolopyridines, bis-pyrazolopyridines and pyrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyrimidine derivatives. The excellent conversions show that the catalyst has strong and sufficient acidic sites, which are responsible for its catalytic performance. After the reaction, the catalyst/product separation could be easily achieved with an external magnetic field, and more than 95% of the catalyst could usually be recovered. The catalyst was reused at least five times without any loss of its high catalytic activity.

Keywords : Magnetically recoverable nanocatalyst, sonochemical procedure, chemoselectivity, aqueous medium.

Introduction

The utilization of catalysis to achieve the goals of green chemistry has met with tremendous success¹. Through the use of catalytic systems, the dual goals of attaining environmental and economic benefit simultaneously are being realized in applications ranging from very small-scale fine chemical synthesis to commodity petrochemical processes. The societal pressure has been at the origin of the concept of nanoscience, which is an exponentially growing research field in modern science that involves the synthesis and application of nanoparticles of different sizes and shapes. It is highly probable that recyclability will be the bottleneck for the industrial application of NPs catalysis in solution phase. Good dispersion of NPs within a solvent is a double edged sword. It usually results in a catalytic system with high activity under mild reaction conditions. Meanwhile, it makes separation of the catalyst from the product more complicated.

Much attention has been directed toward the fabrication of magnetic nanoparticles because they have both fundamental and practical values due to their potential applications in chemical and materials science². The strategy of magnetic separation, taking advantage of magnetic nanoparticles, is typically more effective than filtration or centrifugation as it prevents loss of the catalyst³. Magnetic separation of supermagnetic nanoparticles is simple, economical, and promising for industrial applications⁴.

Use of ultrasound as a means of accelerating reactions has long been known in both industry and academia. Nevertheless, the “green” value of the nonhazardous acoustic radiation has been recognized by synthetic and environmental chemists recently⁵. The role of sonochemistry in the creation of “benign by-design” synthetic methods is clear from the definition : low level of waste, inherently safe, and energy-saving, with an optimized use

[†]In honour of Professor K. C. Joshi on the occasion of his 88th birthday.

of nonrenewable resources, and a preferential exploitation of renewable ones. The application of ultrasound in organic synthesis has been increasing because of its advantages such as shorter reaction times, milder reaction condition, and higher yields in comparison with the classical methods⁶. The chemical and physical effects of ultrasound arise from the cavitation collapse which produces extreme conditions locally and thus induce the formation of chemical species, not easily attained under conventional conditions⁷.

Pyrazoles are a class of heterocyclic compounds having many derivatives with a wide range of interesting properties, such as cyclooxygenase-2 inhibitors (e.g. SC-558, tepoxalin, and celecoxib)^{8,9} and cannabinoid-1 inverse agonists, which are very promising for reducing obesity (e.g. rimonabant)¹⁰. Fused pyrazoles, and pyrazolopyridines in particular, also display a variety of interesting pharmacological properties¹¹, besides finding applications as fluorescence standards and luminophores in organic light emitting diodes¹² (Fig. 1).

A literature survey revealed that although a number of methods have been reported for the synthesis of pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridines¹³. All of these procedures suffered from one or more of the following disadvantages such as long reaction times, low yields of the products, harsh reaction conditions, use of excessive amounts of reagents, tedious workup procedures, and co-occurrence of several side reactions. In addition, some of the catalysts and reagents are expensive, toxic, and air sensitive. Thus, still there is a need to search for better catalysts that could be superior to the existing ones in terms of toxicity, handling, and operational simplicity.

In continuation of our efforts on synthesis of nanomaterials and their application in heterocyclic synthesis¹⁴ and our continued work on ultrasonic-assisted organic synthesis¹⁵ we report herein the synthesis, characterization of iron oxide NPs and their catalytic application for chemoselective synthesis of pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridine derivatives in aqueous medium under ultrasonic irradiation.

Fig. 1. Representatives of pyrazolopyridine containing drugs.

Results and discussion

The first step in the accomplishment of this goal was the convenient synthesis of iron oxide nanocatalyst. A simple aqueous chemical method¹⁶ has been used to prepare these nanomaterials. The entire process was carried out in distilled water for its inherent advantages as it is simple, cost effective, environment friendly, easily scaled up for large scale synthesis and in this method there is no need to use high pressure, temperature and toxic chemicals. The catalyst has been characterized by XRD, TEM, EDAX, etc. XRD pattern of iron oxide NPs is shown in Fig. 2, the position and relative intensities of all peaks confirm well. The samples show intense and broad diffraction peaks at 2θ values of about 26.66, 39.19, 46.51 and 55.95 which correspond to the (202), (203), (213) and (306) planes of iron oxide NPs respectively. A TEM image of iron oxide NPs is shown in Fig. 3. It was confirmed that the catalyst was made up of nanometer-sized particles ~ 17 nm and they are approximately spherical in shape. EDAX of powder sample of iron oxide NPs shows iron and oxygen to be in a stoichiometric atomic ratio.

Fig. 2. XRD analysis of the iron oxide NPs.

Fig. 3. TEM images of the iron oxide NPs.

To examine the catalytic activity of nanoparticles, benzaldehyde **1a**, ethyl cyanoacetate **2** and 3-amino-5-methylpyrazol **3** were employed as reactants for the model reaction in water under sonication. Initially, the mixture was treated with an ultrasonic irradiation for 160 min. However the results demonstrated the need of a catalyst. Initially we focused on the systematic evaluation of different catalysts for the model reaction. A wide variety of catalysts including *p*-TSA, L-proline, InCl_3 , bulk iron oxide, iron oxide NPs, etc. were employed to test their efficacy for the chemoselective synthesis of pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridine-5-carbonitriles. The results presented in Table 1 show that in presence of iron oxide NPs, the desired product was obtained in 96% yield within 10 min. Iron oxide NPs exhibit higher TOF value than other catalyst in this reaction. Therefore, this catalyst appears to be superior to any of the other catalysts tested. The quantity of the catalyst plays a vital role for the formation of the desired product. The best yields were found in the presence of 5 mol% iron oxide NPs. A higher amount of catalyst did not improve the results to an appreciable extent.

Table 1. Comparison of catalytic activity of iron oxide NPs with other catalysts

Entry	Condition	Time (min)	Yield (%) [*]	TOF (h^{-1})
1	–	160	38	–
2	<i>p</i> -TSA (10 mol%) ^a	130	47	26
3	L-Proline (10 mol%) ^a	110	52	50
4	InCl_3 (10 mol%) ^a	84	60	71
5	Bulk iron oxide (10 mol%) ^a	30	71	140
6	Iron oxide NPs (10 mol%) ^a	10	96	238
7	Iron oxide NPs (5 mol%) ^a	10	96	502
8	Iron oxide NPs (5 mol%) ^b	80	76	103

^aReactions are performed on a 2 mmol scale of the reactants in sonication. ^bIn conventional condition. ^{*}Isolated yield.

In order to develop a viable approach, the model reaction was investigated under different nonconventional and conventional conditions and the overall findings are given in Table 1. Under US, the catalytic activity of iron oxide NPs was found to be 5-fold higher than the conventional method. Under ultrasonic irradiation, the cavitation effects form microjets of liquid bombard the surface of catalyst. This effect causes the exposition of unreacted surfaces of catalyst and increasing the inter-phase surface able to react which enhance the catalyst efficiency. With the initial results in hand, a series of experiments were performed using various solvents. The superiority of water as solvent as compared to commonly employed organic solvents is quite clearly evident from the results summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Effect of solvent on the chemoselective synthesis of pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridine derivatives (**4a**)^d

Entry	Solvent	Time (min)	Yield (%)*
1	Ethanol	10	71
2	Methanol	10	68
3	Acetonitrile	10	43
4	DMF	10	47
5	THF	10	51
6	Water	10	96

^dReactions are performed on a 2 mmol scale of the reactants and 5 mol% of catalyst under ultrasonic irradiation.

*Isolated yield.

Multicomponent condensation reactions of 5-aminopyrazoles with active methylene compounds and aromatic aldehydes are often associated with numerous side products as dehydrogenated pyrazolopyridines¹⁷, bis-pyrazolopyridines and pyrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyrimidine derivatives^{18,19} due to selectivity issue and formation of pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridines arising due to presence of nonequivalent nucleophilic reaction centers in the aminopyrazole building block^{20,21}, while the present approach demonstrated exclusive chemoselectivity towards the formation of pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridine derivatives (Scheme 1).

Among the two possible reaction centres viz. NH₂-C=N and NH₂-C-CH, the reaction proceeds via NH₂-

C=N nucleophilic centre, which after subsequent cyclization leads to the formation of pyrazolo[1,5-*a*]pyrimidine selectively. The above observation was further supported by absence of characteristic singlet for the pyrazole methine near 6.0 ppm in the proton NMR spectrum (Fig. 4).

These excellent preliminary results encouraged us to further explore the applicability of the catalyst for the chemosynthesis of pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridine-5-carbonitrile derivatives (Table 3). To study the scope and limitations of this protocol, we have employed a wide range of aromatic and hetero-aromatic aldehydes. In general, aldehydes bearing electron-donating or electron-withdrawing functional groups at different positions reacted smoothly to generate the corresponding products in good to excellent yields.

The ¹H NMR spectra of the products indicated the formation of two diastereoisomers (*cis* and *trans*). The ¹H NMR spectrum of a mixture of *cis* and *trans* isomer of **4a** is presented in Fig. 5. We found that *trans* isomer was formed in more ratio compared to *cis* isomer.

A conceivable mechanism for the formation of the product would be as follows. The iron oxide NPs facilitate the Knoevenagel type coupling through Lewis acid sites (Fe³⁺) coordinated to the oxygen of carbonyl groups. On the other hand, iron oxide NPs can activate methylene compounds so that deprotonation of the C-H bond occurs in the presence of Lewis basic sites (O²⁻). As a result the formation of pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridine derivatives proceeds by activation of reactants through both Lewis acid and basic sites of iron oxide NPs.

Recycling experiments were performed by the reaction of benzaldehyde **1a**, ethyl cyanoacetate **2** and 3-amino-5-methylpyrazole **3** in water. The model reaction was carried out by using 5 mol% of catalyst and the experiments were suitably scaled up. When the reaction was complete, iron oxide NPs could be placed on the side wall of the reaction vessel with the aid of an external magnet and water was removed from the mixture to leave a residue (including the product and catalyst). Then, the product was dissolved in ethanol and the catalyst easily separated from the product by attaching an external magnet onto the reaction vessel, followed by decantation of the product solution. The remaining catalyst was washed with diethyl ether to remove the residual product, dried

Scheme 1. Chemoselective synthesis of pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridine derivatives.

Fig. 4. Two chemoselective products.

under vacuum and reused in a subsequent reaction. More than 95% of the catalyst could usually be recovered from each reaction. In a test of five cycles (Fig. 6), the catalyst could be reused without any significant loss to its catalytic activity. The reason is that the characteristics obtained from TEM of fresh and used catalysts are similar, which suggest the retention of structure and morphology

of iron oxide NPs after repeated use as catalyst except a minute change in the particle size distribution. According to ICP-AES results, there was no nanocatalyst present in the final product.

Experimental

General :

All the chemicals used were of research grade and were used without further purification. IR spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu FT IR-8400S spectrometer using KBr pellets. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ using TMS as an internal standard on a Bruker spectrometer at 300 and 75 MHz respectively. Mass spectrum of representative compound was recorded on JEOL SX-102 spectrometer at 70 eV. The reactions were carried out using an ultrasonic processor probe (Processor SONOPROS PR-1000 MP, OSCAR ULTRASONICS with power input 230 V, 50 Hz, 4 Amps and power variac 0-230 V and 3 Amps) operating at 20 kHz, 750 W with 6 mm/12 mm tip diameter probes.

Table 3. Synthesis of pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridine-5-carbonitrile derivatives under sonication (**4a-f**)

Sr. no.	Ar	Time (min)	Product	Yield (%)*	<i>trans</i> : <i>cis</i> ratio	M.p. (°C)
1.		90	62 : 38	292–294		
2.		92	58 : 42	> 300		
3.		94	66 : 34	> 300		
4.		92	63 : 37	> 300		
5.		91	67 : 33	> 300		
6.		88	66 : 34	> 300		

Fig. 5. The ^1H NMR signals of the *cis* and *trans* isomers of 4-phenyl-3-methyl-6-oxo-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro-2H-pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridine-5-carbonitrile (**4a**).

Fig. 6. Recyclability of iron oxide NPs.

Catalyst characterization :

The size and morphology of the synthesized assembly was observed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) using a JEOL 1011 at an accelerating voltage of 200 kV. Magnetic measurements were performed using a vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM, LakeShore, VSM-7410, USA). Micromeritics ASAP 2020 surface area and porosity analyser was used to calculate the surface area and pore diameter and the samples were degassed at 250 °C

for four hours prior to analysis. X-Ray diffraction (XRD) measurements for phase determination were recorded by Philips powder diffractometer (PW3040/60) with Cu K α radiation (1.54060 nm) operating in a continuous mode to collect 2θ values with a scan rate of 0.02°/min. FT-IR spectra were recorded on a JASCO FT-IR (FT/IR- 6100 type A) spectrometer using KBr pellets.

Preparation of iron oxide nanoparticles :

The size controlled iron oxide nanoparticles were synthesized via co-precipitation method. First of all 10 mM solution of ferric chloride (FeCl_3) was prepared in 100 ml distil water and then the solution was boiled till it was dark red in color. The mixture was reduced by dropwise adding ammonia (NH_3) solution under vigorous stirring at 80 °C under nitrogen gas environment maintaining pH ~ 7.0 during the reaction. After mixing the NH_3 into FeCl_3 solution, a brownish-red solid formed immediately, which was allowed to crystallize completely for another 24 h under rapid stirring. The brownish-red precipitate

settled down on putting off the stirrer. The precipitated nanoparticles were washed by repeated cycles in high speed centrifuge at 10,000 rpm at room temperature. After sufficient drying, the obtained iron oxide was crushed to fine powder with the help of mortar and pestle.

*General procedure for chemoselective synthesis of pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridine-5-carbonitrile derivatives :*

A mixture of benzaldehyde **1a** (2.0 mmol), ethyl cyanoacetate **2** (2.0 mmol) and 3-amino-5-methylpyrazole **3** (2.0 mmol) and 5 mol% iron oxide NPs in 20 ml water was introduced in a heavy walled pear-shaped two-necked flask with non-standard taper outer joint. The flask was attached to a 12 mm tip diameter probe and the reaction mixture was sonicated for 10 min at 50% power of the processor and in a 4 s pulse mode till a solid product separates out. Completion of the reaction was monitored by TLC using *n*-hexane-ethyl acetate (7 : 3) as the eluent. When the reaction was complete, iron oxide NPs could be placed on the side wall of the reaction vessel with the aid of an external magnet, and water was removed from the mixture to leave a residue (including the product and catalyst). Then, the product was dissolved in ethanol and the catalyst easily separated from the product by attaching an external magnet onto the reaction vessel, followed by decantation of the product solution. This solution was concentrated at room temperature to generate the crude product. The crude products were purified by crystallization from ethanol.

Recycling procedure :

After completion of the reaction, the catalyst was separated by an external magnet followed by washing with ethanol. The catalyst was then reused directly for the next round of reaction without further purification.

Conclusion

In summary, an extensive and systematic study identified iron oxide as a heterogeneous, green, and reusable catalyst for the chemoselective synthesis of pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridine-5-carbonitriles via three-component reaction of 3-amino-5-methylpyrazole, ethyl cyanoacetate, and aromatic aldehydes. A variety of pyrazolo[3,4-*b*]pyridine-5-carbonitriles are accessible under mild conditions using this method. The preparation of the catalyst is simple, inexpensive, non-corrosive and environmentally benign.

The catalyst can be easily separated and reused without substantial loss in activity.

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